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INTERROGATING THE NEXUS BETWEEN CORRUPTION AND FDI, EXCHANGE RATE, ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA (1995-2024)

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ABSTRACT

The Nigerian government has implemented a number of anti-corruption initiatives and policies to tackle the scourge of corruption and enhance economic growth. Despite these reforms, the problem has persisted and continues to undermine economic growth in the country. In an attempt to ameliorate these challenges, this study investigated the extent to which corruption affected foreign direct investment, exchange rate and economic growth. The study employed secondary data from National Bureau of Statistics publications and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. Data analysis was carried out using the ARDL estimation technique. The study found that corruption perception index (CPI) (coefficient = -1.96; $p = 0.61 > 0.05$) had a negative but negligible impact on Nigeria's economic expansion. The outcome also demonstrated that foreign direct investment is positively impacted by CPI (coefficient = 0.69; $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Additionally, the exchange rate was significantly and favorably impacted by the CPI (coefficient = 0.48; $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Based on these results, the study came to the conclusion that foreign direct investment and the exchange rate in Nigeria were positively correlated with the corruption perception score. As a result, the report suggested that the Nigerian government should strengthen anti-corruption agencies to effectively combat corruption and implement policies that improve the business environment, infrastructure, and regulatory framework in order to attract more foreign direct investment.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important global issues facing the modern world is undoubtedly corruption. The problems of corruption have received a lot of attention on a global scale, especially in the last thirty years. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development includes a specific goal to combat corruption because the international community (United Nations Members States) has

acknowledged its detrimental effects on nations and their populations. According to Transparency International (2024), corruption is a growing worldwide threat that does much more than impede growth because it is a major contributor to deteriorating democracy, instability, and human rights abuses. Every country and the international community must prioritize combating corruption in the long run. This is crucial in order to combat authoritarianism and ensure a society that is free and peaceful.

There have been several conversations and postulations by scholars as to what constitute corruption. It is also an acceptable fact amongst scholars that there is no clear, consensual and universal definition of corruption, as the concept enmeshed in ambiguity. Most scholars defined it based on their field of endeavors and specialization. However, depending on the dimension and perception it is viewed, the definition should capture and explain the monster as is it. Ani (2020), noted that whatever definition is given to the term corruption, the underlining factor that stands out is the evil nature of corruption and those who are engaged in it knows it.

Etymologically, corruption is derived from the Latin term "corruptus," which means "to break or destroy, to depart from morality, ethics, law, and civic virtues (ICPC, 2022). Corruption, according to Transparency International (2023), is the misuse of authority for personal benefit. According to the ICPC Act of 2000, corruption is simply defined as bribery, fraud, and other related offenses. Corruption is "the abuse of public trust and/or office for private or political gains," according to the World Bank (2023). When an official takes, solicits, or demands a bribe, it is considered abuse of public office for personal benefit. Public office is also said to be abused when private agents deliberately give bribes to go around laws and procedures in order to get a competitive advantage and profit (2020, Ani). Corruption is failing to do what you ought to do (Dongban-Mensem, 2024). Bahoo et al. (2020) define corruption as "an illegal activity (bribery, fraud, financial crime, abuse, falsification, favouritism, nepotism, manipulation, etc) conducted through misuse of authority or power by public (government) or private (firms) officeholders for private gain and benefit, financial or otherwise. Osoba cited in Attah et al. (2019) gives a more succinct definition of corruption as: a form of anti-social behaviour by an individual or social group which confers unjust or fraudulent benefits on its perpetrators, is inconsistent with the established legal norms and prevailing moral ethos of the land and is likely to subvert or diminish the capacity of the legitimate authorities to provide fully for the material and spiritual wellbeing of all members of society in a just and equitable manner.

Economic growth on the other hand is one of the fundamental macroeconomic policy objectives countries all over the world strive to achieve as it is a necessary prerequisite for economic development (Bonga & Thabani, 2018). The World Bank noted that "economic growth is conventionally measured as the percentage increase in gross domestic product (GDP) or gross national product (GNP) during one year. Ele and Ogbonna (2023) defined economic growth as the increase in a country's potential Gross Domestic Product (GDP) which is measured in a monetary value of final goods and services produced in a country in a given period of time. Tiamiyu, et al (2025) averred that economic growth is a key policy objective of any government that is essential in reducing poverty, create employment opportunities, bridge the inequality and raise the standard of living of the people. Poor economic growth therefore is a reflection of the structural anomalies, poor governance and lack of political leadership with vision resulting in corruption. The consequences of these corrupt practices on economic growth in Nigeria are assumed to be scary and tends to deteriorate the whole economic system.

According to (Transparency International, 2014) corruption has a direct impact on economic growth and development and indirect effects on a country's economic performance by affecting many factors fueling economic growth, such as investment, taxation, composition and effectiveness of public expenditure. Osuma et al. (2024) noted that systemic corruption, in particular, has a profound negative impact on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows, as higher corruption levels correlate with lower levels of foreign investment. Nguyen *et al.* (2021) concluded in their studies that FDI inflows are positively affected by GDP growth and trade openness. In addition, control of corruption has a positive effect on FDI inflows.

Furthermore, corruption significantly impacts exchange rate when it becomes prevalent, it discourages foreign direct investment, increases inflation leading to decrease in the value of the currency (naira) making imports more expensive and causing exchange rate fluctuation. Corruption deters foreign investors, thereby reduces the demand for local currency (naira) and weakens its value. Ramoni-Perazzi & Ramero (2022) in their findings noted that exchange rate volatility has shown to be substantially higher in countries with higher levels of corruption in their government, but decreasing over time, probably due to the adoption of more controlled exchange rate regimes, at least in some periods of greater instability. Junejo et al (2019) find that corruption perception index, and foreign borrowing have positive and significant impact on exchange rate. In Nigeria, the exchange rate trajectory is influenced by certain economic factors including; external reserves in which substantial accretion provide the Central Bank of Nigeria with a formidable cushion to defend the local currency (Naira) and manage market liquidity. Secondly, sustain deflation in the system with a slowing down of headline inflation makes the Naira more attractive to both local and foreign investors thereby enhancing exchange rate stability. Furthermore, since Nigeria economy is anchored on crude oil export, increase in oil production coupled with stable global oil prices, ensures a steady inflow of foreign exchange into the economy thereby stabilizing exchange rate.

The objectives of the study was to interrogate the nexus between Corruption and FDI, Exchange rate, Economic growth in Nigeria. The study focused on the activities of Nigerian economy from 1995 to 2024.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses in null form were tested.

H₀1: There is no significant impact of corruption on economic growth in Nigeria

H₀2: Corruption has no significant effect on foreign direct investment in Nigeria

H₀3. There is no significant impact of corruption on exchange rate in Nigeria

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Corruption

According to Transparency International (2024), corruption is an evolving global threat that does far more than undermine development, as it is a key cause of declining democracy, instability

and human rights violations. Most scholars defined the concept based on their field of endeavors and specialization. Ani (2020), noted that whatever definition is given to the term corruption, the underlining factor that stands out is the evil nature of corruption and those who are engaged in it knows it. Transparency International (2023) defined corruption as the abuse of entrusted power for private gain. The ICPC Act 2000 defined Corruption simply to include bribery, fraud and other related offences. The World Bank (2023) defined corruption as the abuse of public trust and/or office for private or political gains. Corruption is failing to do what you ought to do (Dongban-Mensem 2024). Direct looting of treasury, illicit financial flows, tax evasion, misapplication of funds, budget padding, ghost workers, deliberate elephant projects, project abandonment, and contract and procurement abuse as a result of corruption have huge implications on development and human security (Owasanoye 2022). Abu (2022) sees corruption as unethical behavior which runs counter to the accepted social norms and moral values.

Foreign Direct Investment.

Ashine (2024) averred that foreign direct investment is a type of cross-border investment made by a person who lives in one country (the direct investor) with the aim of acquiring a long-term stake in a company (the direct investment enterprise) that is located in a different country. FDI occurs when a financier from one country puts money into a company in another country with the intent of developing a long-term financial stake in the latter (Emeka, 2024). Ajayi, (2020) opined that foreign direct investment is a potential catalyst for economic growth and development, it serves as a vital source of capital that can drive local market competition, enhance employment opportunities, and facilitate technology transfer, thereby fostering sustainable economic development and reducing poverty (Osuma et al. 2024). However, attracting foreign direct investment is not without challenges such as political instability, corruption, and macroeconomic policies, have been identified as significant impediments to foreign direct investment in Nigeria (Osuma et al. 2024).

Exchange Rate

An exchange rate is the relative price of one currency expressed in terms of another currency or group of currencies (Munzhelele, 2024). It is the required amount of units of a currency that can buy another amount of units of another currency (Adeniran et al. 2014). Low and stable exchange rate, can encourage exports and consequently boost economic growth (Oyadeyi et al. 2025). Corruption significantly impacts exchange rate when it becomes prevalent, it discourages foreign direct investment, increases inflation leading to decrease in the value of the currency (naira) making imports more expensive and causing exchange rate fluctuation (Ramoni-Perazzi & Ramero, 2022). Corruption deters foreign investors, thereby reduces the demand for local currency (naira) and weakens its value (Junejo et al. 2019)

Theoretical Framework

Sand in the Wheel Theory

This study is anchored on sand in the wheel theory which was propounded by Myrdal 1968. The theory assumed that corruption, foreign direct investment and exchange rate decreases economic growth because corruption prevents efficient production and innovation as it distort inflow of foreign investment and exchange rate. Gründler & Potrafke (2019) noted that empirical

evidences suggest that corruption, exchange rate and foreign direct investment decreases economic growth, especially in countries with low investment rates and low-quality governance. Agostino et al. (2016), Huang, (2016), Tsanana et al. (2016), Chang & Hao (2017) averred that corruption, foreign direct investments and exchange rate obstructs economic growth by diverting officials' attention toward the gains derived from such activities. Scholars in the likes of Paulo, et al. (2022); Oke & Onaolapo (2022); Umana et al. (2022), Lawal et al. (2022); Makar *et al.* (2023), Kenku et al. (2024), have all concluded in their studies that corruption, foreign direct investment and exchange rate lowers economic growth, and are of the biggest barriers to social progress, economic expansion, and poverty alleviation.

Empirical Review

Ozigbo et al (2025) investigated the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on Nigeria's economic development between 1990 and 2023 using the Co-integration Error Correction Mechanism. The analysis found that there was a substantial negative correlation between economic growth and the interest rate and exchange rate. Additionally, within the study's time frame, the inflation rate and external reserve had a large but favorable relationship with economic growth. The study concluded that exchange rate fluctuations and interest rates negatively affect Nigeria's economic growth. The study recommended that policymakers should create measures that can boost Nigeria's production of goods and services in addition to relying on the manipulation of macroeconomic variables to stop short-term swings in exchange rates.

Abdulaziz and Ezeh (2025) examined the relationship between Nigeria's economic development and exchange rates between 1985 and 2023. The research utilized Error Correction Model (ECM) analysis and found that naira depreciation establishes positive statistical links with economic growth rates thus supporting competitiveness and investment expansion. The study results further showed that the relationships between GDP growth, inflation rates and interest rates are positive but FDI and external reserves reveal minimal influence on GDP. The study concluded that external reserves, despite their importance in global financial stability do not significantly impact real GDP growth in the context of Nigeria's current economic conditions. The study recommended that, in order to encourage and ensure viable economic growth in Nigeria, the government have to give great concern to stabilizing the exchange rate through effective monetary policies to attract foreign investors.

Applying the Generalized Moment Estimation Method, Yahyaoui's (2025) investigated FDI inflows and economic growth in four North African nations. The study finds that attracting FDI is mostly dependent on the caliber of institutions and a sophisticated financial system. The study concluded that successfully implementation of the rule of law draws in foreign investment and fosters economic expansion. High levels of corruption reduce the positive effects of foreign direct investment on economic development in these countries. The study recommended that to attract FDI, they four countries must have a strong legal system, a low level of corruption, and fewer bureaucratic roadblocks.

Larasati et al. (2025) used a quantitative method with multiple linear regression and panel data to examine the impact of labor force participation rates, inflation, foreign direct investment (FDI), and corruption control on GDP growth from 2017 to 2024. The study found that labor force participation rates do not significantly affect economic growth, but inflation, foreign direct

investment, and corruption control do. The study concluded that reducing corruption promotes a more favorable business environment, which raises productivity and the flow of foreign investment. The study recommended that the ASEAN countries should make efforts to maintain inflation at a reasonable level to support sustainable economic growth, and also should improve on corruption control policies so as to attract foreign investment.

Martinez (2024) investigated how corruption affected growth and investment in Canada's impoverished areas. A desk technique was used in the study. The result of the study shows that corruption seriously impedes investment and development in impoverished areas, impeding economic expansion and escalating inequality. The study came to the conclusion that corruption hinders the accomplishment of sustainable development goals and reduces the efficacy of development activities. The study suggested putting policies in place to improve governance institutions' accountability, openness, and rule of law.

Guha et al. (2020) investigated whether corruption lowers foreign direct investment inflows into every developing nation. The study's findings indicate that, despite their similar levels of corruption, developing nations with high growth rates get more foreign direct investment than those with low growth rates. Because foreign direct investment inflows are sensitive to higher growth rates, the study found that developing nations should enhance their investment climate and implement institutional changes to boost their growth rates.

Employing the ARDL econometric analysis, Fayad and Taher (2024), evaluated the effect of corruption on the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) nations' economic development between 2000 and 2020. Using data from Transparency International and the World Bank, the study estimates how corruption affects GDP growth in the MENA region. According to the study, corruption does considerably impede economic growth, but at different corruption index variables. The report suggested that MENA countries implement a number of policy changes. First, there is a need for quicker changes that would improve accountability and transparency, particularly in the sectors that are prone to corruption, such as natural resources and governmental procurement. Second, for anti-corruption legislation to be implemented effectively, the institutional framework—which consists of the judiciary, law enforcement, and independent anti-corruption organizations—must be strengthened. The study further recommended that anti-corruption strategies should be developed, to reflect specific local contexts and sector challenges.

Using panel data regression with a fixed-effect model, Husna and Nasir (2024) examine the role of corruption, foreign direct investment, and unemployment in ASEAN-5 countries of; (Indonesia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Laos, and Thailand) from 2012 to 2022. The results indicated that foreign direct investment (FDI) has a significant positive effect on economic growth, while corruption perception index and unemployment have no significant impact in the ASEAN-5 countries. The study recommended the strengthening anti-corruption measures, enhancing transparency, and improving governance. More so addressing unemployment requires investing in education and skills training, promoting entrepreneurship, and creating a business-friendly environment for job creation.

Ajayi et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between corruption and economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1996 to 2020. The study employed the Fully Modified

Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method and Granger causality tests for data analysis. The results showed that both gross fixed capital formation and urbanization significantly and positively influence economic growth in Nigeria, whereas the corruption index has a negative and significant effect which align with the "sand the wheels" theory. In light of the above result, the study recommended that policymakers prioritise transparency and good governance by implementing e-governance initiatives to reduce bureaucratic hurdles and opportunities for corruption. Furthermore, there should be consistent monitoring and thorough evaluation of the impact of anti-corruption strategies on economic growth and development to ensure their effectiveness.

Kenku et al. (2024) investigated Corruption in Nigeria: An implication to national development. According to the study, corruption has a number of negative effects on Nigeria's growth, including impeding a number of socioeconomic indices that would have helped the country become developed. The study's findings shows that Nigeria's economic growth and development have been adversely impacted by corruption, which has led to a lack of public infrastructure, a rise in poverty despite the country's abundant resources, and lack of respect for fundamental human rights. The study recommended that government should strengthen the ability of the anti-graft agencies and at best make them independent from the influence of political elites. Also, between 1996 and 2022, employing ARDL Model, Ijirshar et al. 2024, evaluated the relationship between corruption control and economic growth in Nigeria and found that control of corruption has weak positive influence on economic growth in Nigeria in the long run but a strong negative influence on economic growth in the short-run. The study concluded that in the long run, there is a positive but significant effect of control of corruption and economic growth in Nigeria, implying that the control of corruption mechanisms in Nigeria are weak in yielding strong positive influence on economic growth. The study recommended that the Nigerian government should intensify efforts to create more agencies beside EFCC and ICPC to address cases of corrupt practices in the economy and encourage leaders that display transparency, honesty, probity, accountability, purposefulness and commitment to good ideals of the society.

Makar et al. (2023) looked at how corruption affected Nigeria's economic growth between 1986 and 2019. The study employed vector error correction tests and the Johansen co-integration test. According to the study, rising levels of corruption considerably impede Nigeria's economic growth over time, but they have little effect in the short term. The study's findings indicated that corruption stymies Nigeria's economic expansion. The study recommended that in fighting corruption, Nigeria requires good and virtuous leaders who are honest with integrity, discipline and trustworthiness. Similarly, Ishfaq and Waqas (2023) used vector error correction model (VECM) analysis to examine how corruption affected economic growth in Pakistan between 1996 and 2021. The results reveal that trade openness promotes growth. The GDP growth rate is negatively impacted by corruption and inflation. The study concluded that corruption is pervasive throughout Pakistan and the country remains one of the most corrupt country on earth. The study recommended that Pakistan could achieve faster economic growth if it could curb widespread corruption.

Setiana, et al (2023) examined how trade liberalization, foreign direct investment, and corruption affected Indonesia's economic expansion between 1995 and 2019. Data analysis techniques used included path analysis and autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL). The study found that, foreign direct investment boosts economic growth in the short term but has no long-term impact, but

trade openness has a detrimental short-term and long-term impact. The study recommended that the Indonesian government should focus more of their policies on the productive side rather than the consumptive side of trade openness to increase technological development and improve the quality of the utilization of both natural and human resources.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used an ex-post facto research design, which entails gathering and evaluation of existing or published data relating to past events. The design was also chosen because of the availability of existing literature on the subject matter. The study was conducted between 1995 and 2024, a span of thirty years. The choice of the base year is informed by the fact that it was the year Transparency International (TI), the global ranking body began the ranking of nations and regions worldwide by their perceived levels of public sector corruption. The year 2024 was chosen due to availability of data. The study uses secondary data throughout the process.

3.2 Population of the Study

The study population comprise of all the macroeconomic variables that affect economic expansion in Nigeria. Nonetheless, data are source from the Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria for the period 1995-2024 for analysis. More so, data for corruption perceptions index specific to Nigeria was obtained from Transparency International database.

3.3 Sample Frame

The study sampled time series data on corruption indices (corruption perception index) and other macroeconomic variables. The sampled variables included; foreign direct investment and exchange rate covering the period of 30 years (1995-2024). The study used purposive sampling technique as it is suited for the study, as all the variables are relevant to the research objectives.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The study adopts Autoregressive Distribution Lag (ARDL) method which is a collection of regression techniques designed to prevent data points from significant deviation from general trend. In addition, Granger Causality test and Johansen co-integration model is used. These techniques are desirable as they can be effectively applied on time series data that captures both short and long run relationship. The study also tests the stationarity (Unit root) of the data to avoid spurious regression results.

3.6 Measurement of Variables

Table 1: Measurement of variables

S/N	Variables	Types	Measurement	Source
1	Economic Growth Rate	Dependent Variable	Current Year's GDP – Previous Year's GDP/Previous Year's GDP X 100	CBN Statistical Bulletin (Various Issues)

2	Foreign Direct Investment	Dependent Variable	This is an investment made by (individuals and corporate bodies) in another country.	CBN Statistical Bulletin (Various Issues)
3	Exchange Rate	Dependent Variable	The relative value of one currency stated in terms of another currency or set of currencies is known as an exchange rate.	(Munzhele, 2024)
4	Corruption	Independent Variable	Corruption Perceptions Index	Transparency International (2024)

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2026.

3.7 Model Specification

The model adapted for this study is underpinned to the work of Ndem, *et al.* (2022) who studied Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach (ARDL) to Corruption and Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria. The baseline model is expressed as:

$$GDPGR = f(COR, FDI, INFL, TOP, LITR) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

This study adjusted the model by removing the variables such as inflation, trade openness and literacy rate and replacing them with economic growth indicators such as foreign direct investment and exchange rate as a function of corruption. This is to show the nexus of the individual variables as it effect corruption and how it has affected the growth of the economy.

Therefore, the models are as follows;

Model 1

$$GDPGR = f(CPI) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Model 2

$$FDI = f(CPI) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Model 3

$$EXR = f(CPI) \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Theoretically, it is expected that independent variable should affect economic growth indicators in Nigeria $b_1 > b_1 < 0$) as a priori expectations, *ceteris paribus*.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Dev.	Jarque-Bera.	Prob.
GDPGR	30	4.485000	-1.790000	15.33000	3.499048	4.884130	0.086981
LCPI	30	2.635454	-1.660731	3.332205	1.229614	47.37215	0.000000
LEXR	30	5.042978	3.086030	7.289638	0.995214	0.930113	0.628100
LFDI	30	5.576637	-0.294908	7.366599	1.858025	16.92851	0.000211

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

The descriptive results presented in Table 2 indicate that the Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate (GDPGR) in Nigeria during the period of 30years (1995-2024) has min and max values of -1.79 and 15.33 respectively. GDPGR averaged 4.49 with a std. dev. of 3.50 implying that the data deviate from both sides of the mean by 3.5, suggesting a widely dispersion of GDPGR in Nigeria during the period under investigation. This could be attributed to systemic corruption and inconsistent policy changes that characterized different administrations in Nigeria over time. The descriptive normality results also showed that GDPGR is normally distributed. This was captured by the Jarque-Bera probability value of 0.09, found to be greater than 0.05. The table 2 further showed that LCPI has min and max values of -1.66 and 3.33 respectively. The average value of LCPI during the period is 2.64 with a std. dev.1.23. The p-value 0.00 for Jarque-Bera revealed that normal data distribution was not met at a 5% level of significance, indicating high level of corruption. Furthermore, EXR has min and max values of (3.09, 7.29) respectively. The average value of exchange rate during the period is 5.04 with a std dev of 0.99. Also, the p-value 0.63 for Jarque-Bera indicated meeting the assumption of normal distribution as it was above 5% level of significance. FDI, has min and max values of (-0.30, 7.37) respectively. The average value was 5.58 with a std dev 1.86, Also, the p-value of 0.000 for Jarque-Bera implies that the Gaussian distribution assumption of normal data was not met at a 5% level of significance as a result of outliers.

Correlation Matrix of variables

Table 3

	GDPGR	LCPI	LEXR	LFDI
GDPGR	1			
LCPI	0.124649	1		
LEXR	-0.088317	0.805639	1	
LFDI	0.223438	0.858692	0.708793	1

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

Correlation matrix is mostly used to check for multi-collinearity and the association between explanatory variable (LCPI) and the dependent variables (LGDPGR, LCPI, LFDI, and LEXR). As shown in Table 3 there was statistical evidence that GDPGR and LCPI has weak positive associated at (12.5%). This implied no substantial detrimental effect of corruption on economic growth. Exchange rate has a very strong positive association with CPI at (81%). This suggested the presence of round-tripping or exchange rate racketeering. Foreign direct investment also has a strong positive relationship with CPI (86%). This implied that lower corruption in an economy boost investor's confidence and attract more foreign direct investment.

ADF Unit Roots Test

Table 4

Variable	ADF-Statistics	Critical Value @ 5%	Integrated Order	Prob	Remarks
LGDPGR	-2.986352	-2.967767	I (0)	0.0481	Stationary @level
LCPI	-3.815784	-2.991878	I (0)	0.0084	Stationary @level
LFDI	-3.681383	-2.967767	I (0)	0.0100	Stationary @level
EXR	-4.728973	-2.971853	I (1)	0.0008	Stationary @1 st difference

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

According to the unit root test results presented in Table 4, EXR is stationary at first difference, but GDPGR, CPI, and FDI are stationary at level. This suggested the Granger causality test for suitable features of this data and the Johansen cointegration test to examine the long- and short-term relationships among the variables.

Johansson Co-integration

Table 5 An overview of Johansson Co-integration variables

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	69.44961	47.85613	0.0002	44.24682	27.58434	0.0002
At most 1	25.20279	29.79707	0.1543	18.05064	21.13162	0.1280
At most 2	7.152147	15.49471	0.5600	6.936962	14.26460	0.4966
At most 3	0.215185	3.841466	0.6427	0.215185	3.841466	0.6427

Source: Author's Computation, (2026)

The Trace and Max-eigen statistics for the Johansen co-integration test are shown in Table 5 above.

At the 5% level, both statistics demonstrated the existence of at least one co-integrating equation. To reject the null hypothesis that there is no co-integration, at least one co-integrating equation must exist. Therefore, the Trace test indicated one co-integrating equations, while the Max-eigen statistics also show one co-integrating equation. This surpasses the decision criteria and so the

study rejects the null hypothesis and concluded that there is long run relationship between corruption perception index, foreign direct investment, exchange rate and gross domestic product in Nigeria. More so, that both tests confirm at least 1 long-run co-integrating relationship among the variables. The vector error correction model (VECM) can be tested for each model separately as long as the variables are co-integrated. The practical result is that the variables tend to move together over time, even in the face of short-term shocks.

Pairwise granger causality test

Table 6. An Overview of Causality Test of Variables

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Sample: 1995 2024

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
LCPI does not Granger Cause GDPR	28	0.07212	0.9306
GDPR does not Granger Cause LCPI		0.49687	0.6148
LEXR does not Granger Cause LCPI	28	3.40406	0.0507
LCPI does not Granger Cause LEXR		1.46984	0.2508
LFDI does not Granger Cause LCPI	28	0.47005	0.6308
LCPI does not Granger Cause LFDI		4.90496	0.0168

Source: Author's Computation, (2026)

Table 6 indicated that there is no causality between GDPGR and LCPI, LCPI and LEXR, LFDI and LCPI. The results further revealed uni-directional causality between LCPI and LEXR and LFDI and LCPI respectively.

Regression Analyses

Table: 7 Overview of Regression Analysis for objective 1 GDPGR on CPI

Dependent Variable: GDPR

Method: ARDL

Sample (adjusted): 1995 2024

Included observations: 26 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
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LCPI	-1.962192	3.817795	-0.513960	0.6135
C	6.684854	12.05860	0.554364	0.5862
R-squared	0.720229	Durbin-Watson stat		1.829843
Adjusted R-squared	0.611429			
F-statistic	6.619761			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000578			

Source: Author's Computation, 2026

The Autoregression distribution lag (ARDL) results estimated coefficient of -1.96 ($p=0.61>0.05$) reveal that corruption perception index has negative insignificant influence on economic growth in Nigeria. That is a unit increase in the corruption perception index is associated with 1.96 units decrease in economic growth. By implication corruption have a statistically detrimental insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Regression Analyses

Table: 8 Overview of Regression Analysis for objective 3 FDI on CPI

Dependent Variable: LFDI

Method: ARDL

Sample (adjusted): 1995 2024

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LCPI	0.693754	0.246823	2.810734	0.0093
C	2.200931	0.469222	4.690600	0.0001
R-squared	0.746896	Durbin-Watson stat		1.747424
Adjusted R-squared	0.727426			
F-statistic	38.36226			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's Computation, (2026)

The ARDL in objective 3 results estimated coefficient of 0.69 ($p=0.001<0.05$) reveal that corruption perception index has positive significant influence on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. That is a unit increase in the corruption perception index is associated with 0.69 units improvement in FDI. This implies that foreign direct investment positively affects corruption in Nigeria as it result in increased capital formation and innovation

Regression Analyses

Table: 9 Overview of Regression Analysis for objective 2 EXR on CPI

Dependent Variable: LEXR

Method: ARDL

Sample (adjusted): 1995 2024

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LCPI	0.484200	0.090360	5.358563	0.0000
C	-0.743927	0.277928	-2.676691	0.0141
R-squared	0.971387	Durbin-Watson stat		1.947938
Adjusted R-squared	0.964575			
F-statistic	142.5882			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

The ARDL results estimated coefficient of 0.48 ($p=0.00<0.05$) reveal that corruption perception index has positive significant impact on exchange rate in Nigeria. That is a unit increase in the corruption perception index (reduction in corruption) is associated with 0.48 unit increase in exchange rate. By implication exchange rate have a strong statistically significant effect on corruption in Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

Table 7 ARDL analysis results showed that corruption had a statistically favorable but small impact on economic growth. This suggests that corruption has little effect on economic growth.

This is in line with the a priori expectation of grease the wheel theory, which state that corruption does not harm the economy but rather lubricate the wheel of economic growth as reported in the study of Awadzie and Garr (2021) but in contrary to the work of Ossai (2025), Kenku *et al* (2024), Ajayi et al (2024). In other words the regression analysis's results in table 8 revealed a strong significant association between corruption and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. This implied that improvements in corruption perception index (lower corruption levels) increases the inflow of foreign direct investment into Nigeria. This findings is in line with the work of (Osuma *et al.* 2024, Amade & Oyigebe 2024, Hussaini and Kabuga, 2025). On the contrary, Lestari et al (2022) in their study found that corruption does not have a statistically significant impact on FDI.

In addition, from table 9 above, CPI revealed a strong positive and highly significant effect on exchange rate in Nigeria. This implied that improvement in the level of corruption (lower corruption) result to improved exchange rate stability in Nigeria. This also implied that CPI significantly influences movement in exchange rate. This findings is in line with the work of (Junejo, et al. 2019, Ramoni-Perazzi & Ramero 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

From the study, the results of the analysis demonstrated a positive none-substantial association between corruption and economic growth. Therefore, the study concluded that corruption does not hinder economic growth as it reflects an insignificant improvement on the economy as supported by the grease the wheel theory that corruption lubricate the wheel of an economy.

The study also revealed that corruption perception index do impact foreign direct investment positively, meaning that as the corruption perception index increases corruption level becomes low. Therefore, it was concluded that a decrease in corruption attract more foreign capital inflow into Nigeria, promotes economic expansion, drive growth, and enhances technological transfer and innovation, as investors will have confidence in the country.

The study also shows that corruption has a strong positive effect on exchange rate in Nigeria as it concludes that improvement in corruption perception index (lower corruption) contribute to better economic/investor's confidence and subsequently leading to exchange rate stability. This further implies that changes in corruption perception significantly influences exchange rate.

5.2 Recommendations

In view of the study's results, the following recommendations are applicable:

- i The study recommended that, government should intensified the efforts of anti-corruption agencies (ICPC & EFCC) so as to effectively continue to combat corruption and ensure long term sustainable growth.
- ii The study also recommended that government should develop policies for improving business environments, infrastructure development, and regulatory reforms to attract more foreign direct investment.
- iii The study further recommended that government should continue to sustain the fight against corruption as the dividend of the fight has resulted in exchange rate stability and subsequent confidence in investors.

5.3 Contributions to Knowledge

The study contributed majorly to the comprehensive empirical assessment of corruption impacts on macroeconomic indicators such as economic growth, foreign direct investments, and exchange rate simultaneously in Nigeria. The study further authenticate the use of ARDL as commonly employed by previous researchers.

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